

The Use Of Integrative Reading In Obtaining Information About The Natural-Scientific World In Requirements From Chemistry

Jumanov Akhmadjon Mirzaevich

Associate Professor of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: *This article provides recommendations on the use of innovative technologies in the educational system. Innovative approaches have been involved as key factors in the modernization of Education.*

Keywords — innovation, integration, education, chemistry teaching, quality and results of education, methods of traditional and non-traditional teaching, pedagogical innovation, the leading role of the pedagogical person in the system, current problems of the system of continuing education.

INTRODUCTION

In connection with the announcement by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev that 2024 is the "year of youth and business support", the Center for the introduction of innovative technologies in all areas has set out such tasks as achieving educational efficiency, improving the quality of educational work, training competitive personnel, developing creativity in future specialists. The garden with education is a multifaceted and complex process, consisting of the thought of mind and physical work, collaborative or independent work, activity and creativity of students in the example of teachers and students, in general, receiving knowledge, tutoring, mentoring and mentoring of other responsible individuals, in short, teachers and mentors.

Issues of improving the effectiveness of extracurricular and extracurricular activities are inextricably linked with the establishment of the educational process on a scientific basis and the practical application of modern pedagogical technologies. The main goal of carrying out innovative activities in educational issues, innovating in educational processes and re-developing new approaches is to ensure the cooperation of the team of teachers and students, and its implementation according to a clear plan and goal-oriented. This work requires a public solution to the issues of pedagogy-psychology and Tashkent. It is necessary to take into account that pedagogical innovations manufacturers must thorough knowledge of methodologicpsychological, pedagogical, technological knowledge about the advent, manifestation and process of their management of innovations. Pedagogical innovations are not effective at AKS Khol.

In our opinion, the fulfillment of the requirements for improving the effectiveness of the processes of innovation in the educational system is a link to the conditions for the development and introduction of pedagogical innovation, to the purposeful, rational and self-sufficient application of traditional and modern methods of Education. Cases of abandonment of traditional methods that are effective in some are simple. It has been tested and tested positive in the

implementation of innovations in such a difference as a game against teaching methodology. That is why positive changes in the traditional education system can appeal to innovation. Nowadays, the interest and attention to the application of innovative technologies in the educational system is gaining momentum day by day. The results achieved today are that while the educational goals are being educated, modern technologies are their creative activity, the search for knowledge that has the opportunity to acquire, the conclusion of which is the link with the place of penetration of ham in themselves.

Innovative technologies in the field of pedagogy dictate the use of interactive techniques in the implementation of it in practice, making innovations, modifications to the activities of the teacher and student.

Interactive methods are based on each Information activist, free and independent thinking, recreated in the educational process. This has become an interesting activity to gain knowledge when using methods. Those who have independent work and qualifications in the help and cooperation of students when interactive methods are used. Students acquire new knowledge on the basis of scientific research, research, experimental research. Science orcali is guided by the principle of obtaining knowledge. Participants in the educational process work in small groups. There is no information about reading tasks, but information about all of the small group. Each member of the microguruh acts with their own sense of accomplishing the task. This condition shakes the sense of community in teachers and builds their initiative. The main form of reading process Tashkent is a lesson. Currently, various unconventional images of the lesson are in Joris. Today, taking classes serves to increase creative ability, increase intelligence capacity, expand across the scientific world, and get a quick and complete acceptance of each innovation serves to make vision and skills tremble. The requirements for the application of innovative technologies in the course of the lesson aroused interest in scientific research, the development of creativity and creativity. Education, upbringing and qualifications are practically taught, the quality of change increases. To do this,

the teacher must be skilled and plan the lesson according to the content of the topics, helping all teachers to work actively and healthily during the training session. Zero teacher-general execution of an educational organization. In this, it was important that each reading is set in a short time to change, process and put into practice a very large set of objective information. In solving it, the use of one modern Information Technology, total CDs, with reading methods will help. The use of a lesson computer provides an opportunity to get the teaching process interesting, to personally help each study. In this, first of all, it will be possible to convey a lot of information, facts and information to the high requirements of a wide range of information and communication technologies. Secondly, the fully practical implementation of the innovative plan, ideas and feedback of training begins in a light and effective way. Today, jaroyons are especially picky in chemistry education[1]

In the direction of education" methodology of teaching biology", the course "chemistry" is carried out aimed at improving chemistry and biology in research on improving the content and structure aspect [4]

Both fans are close and sociable, they complement each other and are actively involved in shaking the natural-scientific landscape of the universe as a whole. Considering the fact that the modern world is divided into two types, and the role of fans serving in ensuring the connection between living nature can be imagined as follows (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Inanimate, and the interaction of living nature

The" methodology of teaching biology " of the state educational standards (DTS) in chemistry and Biological Sciences, which are studied in the field of higher education, and the analysis of the content of Education, shows that there is a system of concepts common to them:

- 1) in order and its structural elements;
- 2) phenomena and processes methods of working in them in the ham units of the elements;

- 3) material units that ensure the interaction of inanimate and living nature.

We consider that it is advisable to carry out the teaching of chemistry and Biology on the path to ensuring interdisciplinary communication:

Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan; this is a commonality in the essence of the laws in the fan fund;

Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan; the techniques used in these disciplines are the use of chemistry and biology classes.

We find it necessary to characterize interdisciplinary communication on three views on the same topic:

- a) changing basic concepts common to chemistry and biology;
- b) changing the concepts of basic chemistry;
- c) changing the most important biological concepts.

In the study of chemistry and biology, where natural science is a network of two kings, three types of interdisciplinary communication should be distinguished: the totality of research work, issues, laws and concepts; proportionality of scientific methods;

Information about the Council of the Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In the educational system, we calculate the provision of information on the support of its innovative technologies in future practical activities, not limited to the training of knowledge and educators on the basis of innovative technologies.

The most unique achievement of civilization in return for the integration of fans is introduced by hand [2].

References

[1] Omonov H.T., Mirvohidova M.N. Some of the methodology and methodology of chemistry . Methodical guide. - Tashkent: TDPU. -2002. – 142 B.
 [2] Omonov H.T. The role of integration and differentiation of Sciences in the creation of the scientific picture of the universe. // Journal" Social-Humanities in education", No. 3, 2007. - B.135-138.

- [3] Khojaev V.He., Mamayusupov S., Jumanov A.M. Podgotovka budutshogo uchitelya ximii na osnove innovatsionix technologiy. Issues of improving the teaching of mathematics and Informatics in the system of continuing education” materials of the Republican scientific and practical conference.– Kokdpi, Kokand, 2012. - B.312-314.
- [4] Jumanov A. Some issues of teaching with the improvement of the course “Inorganic Chemistry” for the direction of Biology Education. // Journal" Bulletin of the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy", № 2, 2011. - B.65-70.
- [5] A.M. Jumanov, G.M.Raxmatullaeva, G.S.Meliboeva, (2021). Use Of Experience Gained In The Process Of Teaching Chemistry. The American Journal of Applied Sciences, 3(04), 27-31.
- [6] Jumanov A. About Integrative Improvement of the Course" Chemistry" in the Chemical Preparation of Future Students of Biology. Open Access Repository 8 (6), 60-63
- [7] M.Jumanov, M.A. Ziyomiddinova. Use of innovative technologies in the education system for integration purposes. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 10 (9), 221-224
- [8] M.Nishonov, A.Jumanov. The implementation of interdisciplinary connections as one of the areas of training for a future biology teacher. The World of Education-education in the world, 76-80. A.M.Jumanov, M.M.Sarimsoqova. FORMATION OF PRACTICAL LEARNING SKILLS AND SKILLS OF CHEMISTRY STUDENTS.
- [9] British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development 4, 78-8.
- [10] A.M. Jumanov, R Khaydarov. USING INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS IN TEACHING ELEMENTARY CHEMISTRY.CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS 2 (07), 11-15Writer’s Handbook. Mill Valley, CA: University Science.